

ROLE OF DALIT WOMEN IN MAKING OF VIKSIT BHARAT

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Abstract

Today, India is making progress in many fields, such as technology, politics, science, sports, education, and culture. Women have played a significant role in these areas of growth. At present, women are recognized as actively participating in every sector. In politics, leaders like Indira Gandhi, Mamata Banerjee, and Mayawati have made remarkable contributions to make viksit India. Nowadays, women hold many important positions in universities and factories. Mata Savitribai Phule, regarded as India's first teacher and poet. She educated women from diverse backgrounds in India and worked to introduce a new lifestyle. Despite facing societal and family challenges, many women who came after and acquired education. Countless Dalit women, including Ramabai, Sushila Takbhore, Rajni Tilak, Anita Bharti, Bama, Baby Kamble, Urmila Pawar, and Meenakshi Moon, have contributed shaping a new framework of India and presented themselves as impressive figure for women in the community.

Keywords: Politics, Science, Sports, Education, Culture, Development, Dalit Women, Indira Gandhi, Mayawati

Introduction

Understanding the situation of women is crucial to determining the advancement of the country. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, a renowned scholar, has stated that "Progress of the community is measured by progress of women." As women actively participate in diverse industries and work alongside men in modern India, their expressions of joy demonstrate that our nation is, in fact, moving forward. Despite society's common perception of women as physically weak, history shows that women had dominated over men and that women were participating in outdoor activities like hunting while men were in charge of household chores. This observation highlights that women are not intrinsically weak; instead, they have been made psychologically fragile by social norms. Uda Devi Pasi, who killed 36 British troops by herself, cannot be disregarded when talking about the courage of women. The British were so impressed by her courage when they learned about her gender that they gave her the nickname the Black Cat. India has a plethora of brave women who have been denied opportunities to display their skills and courage due to superstitions, casteism, and untouchability. For example, Arunima Sinha's motivating tale of deciding to ascend Mount Everest while still in the hospital after suffering the loss of one of her legs in a train tragedy. In the end, she climbed the summit despite her physical problem,

accomplishing a feat that brought great honour to nation. This demonstrates the remarkable abilities of women, who are naturally endowed with immense power and are able of carrying out any task. However, the main barriers preventing women from holding high positions in this country have been rooted in poverty, superstition, tradition, and caste prejudice.

Ahilyabai Holkar, an exceptional woman, challenged prevailing social conventions head-on. After her husband was murdered by enemies, tradition and public pressure demanded that she commit Sati on his funeral pyre. Instead, she responded with courage and firmly refused. Over time, she also opposed many outdated customs, beliefs, and superstitions, ultimately proving herself to be an able ruler and a committed social reformer.

Even today, some women remain constrained by ignorance and superstition, so they unable to raise children and support their families effectively. However, many others have moved beyond rigid traditions and conservative expectations, therefore they seen with books rather than kitchen tools and they are seen in office instead of domestic implements. Almost, two centuries, Savitribai Phule pioneered women's education, and for this contribution she is rightly revered in India as a symbol of knowledge.

To understand India's true history, it is crucial to closely study autobiographies written by Dalit women. Some Dalit women have become educated and documented their struggles through life writing, including Sushila Takhbore's "Shikanje Ka Dard", translated as "My Shacked Life: A Dalit Woman's Autobiography", which powerfully portrays the hardships Dalit women endure. Baby Kamble's "The Prisons We Broke" highlights the oppression inflicted by society, while Bama's "Karukku" exposes the painful realities of Dalit women's lives. Many other Dalit women have expressed their experiences through novels, poetry, autobiographies, and other forms of literature, aiming to assert their voices against social injustice, psychological oppression, and the stigma of untouchability.

Review of Literature

Sushila Takhbore's "Shikanje Ka Dard," seen as the first Dalit autobiography within Hindi literature, explores the exploitation, injustice, and oppression faced by Dalit women, highlighting the dual abuse they experienced. The author reflects this theme in her personal narrative. Due to its popularity, this autobiography made a significant impact and was translated into multiple languages. In her autobiography, the author recounts her childhood experiences in school, living with the stigma of being untouchable, and enduring abuse because of her caste. Similar to other authors who address the issue of water in their life stories, this writer also emphasizes the importance of water in schools as a key theme in her autobiography. Dalit women were exploited by their family on one side, and by members of the general people on the other hand.

"Dalit Dynasty and She" is a political satire novel written by **Sanjay Chitranshi** which is mainly influenced by the politics of Uttar Pradesh. In this novel, the author depicts a Dalit woman named Shanti Devi who becomes the first Dalit woman Chief Minister of a huge state like Uttar Pradesh. Another character in this novel is a person named Rama Chandra who plays the role of a true social reformer and inspires the Bahujan to become rulers in Uttar Pradesh. In this novel, the author shows that in a country like India, people of Bahujan community had been victims of exploitation for centuries. When a Dalit woman in Uttar Pradesh named Shanti Devi, for the first time in history, made a policy to do a new work to bring equality in the society, due to which an awareness was seen among the Dalit and backward class people and to a large extent, the people of this society got the opportunity to work in various fields.

The White Tiger, a satirical work by **Arvind Adiga,** has gained significant recognition and popularity in contemporary times. The narrative follows a character named Balram, who hails from a destitute family in Bihar. His father was burdened by debts, and the circumstances in Bihar during that period were dire. The situation was severe, characterized by exploitation, oppression, injustice, corruption, and caste discrimination. Due to his family's financial struggles, Balram had limited

educational opportunities; therefore, he began working at a tea stall and eventually acquired driving skills. When Ashok, the land lord's son, returns from America with his wife, Pinky, he encounters Balram and is immediately taken with him, subsequently hiring Balram as his chauffeur. An unfortunate incident occurs when Pinky Madam is involved in an accident that results in a girl's death; however, due to their wealth, Pinky avoids repercussions while Balram is wrongfully blamed. Living in Delhi with Ashok allows Balram to observe the lavish lifestyles of the wealthy, witnessing their exploitation of others, their bribery, and immoral behaviour's, which incites both his anger and fascination. Ultimately, Balram takes drastic action by murdering Ashok, stealing a substantial amount of money, and went to Bangalore, where he successfully establishes a prosperous business and achieves remarkable wealth. This novel illustrates that despite Balram's humble beginnings, his mindset set him apart, earning him the nickname 'White Tiger' from his school invigilator.

The autobiography **"Karukku" by Bama** is a powerful Tamil narrative that exposes the exploitation, oppression, and untouchability endured by Dalit women. Bama reveals that despite converting to another religion and achieving higher education, she could not escape the deep-rooted stigma of untouchability. Her critique extends beyond Hinduism to highlight the persistence of caste discrimination within Christianity, which she confronts repeatedly throughout her life, facing humiliation at every stage.

Bama vividly describes her village surrounded by natural beauty, contrasting it with the harsh realities of caste-based discrimination she experienced from childhood—in schools, public spaces, and beyond. Untouchability had become so entrenched in her time that even privileged classes feared Dalits' shadows. Although she was unaware of casteism at age five, she keenly felt the discrimination and untouchability in the Society.

Ultimately becoming a school teacher, Bama poignantly expresses the pain of being denied respect due to her Dalit identity, despite her professional achievements. Her autobiography presents the reality of society and cruelty of person.

Material and Methods

The study is based on the books of Babasaheb Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, Jotirao Phule, Baby Kamble, Bama, Sushila Takhbore, Rajni Tilak, and historical book The Tribes and Cast of the Central Provinces of India, and many other books of Dalit writer. Descriptive and analytical approach have been used in this research paper.

Results

Unless we recognize the unique input of women in any area, it appears challenging to achieve any advancements in that area, whether it be social, political, economic, or within business. Just as women manage the home and enhance its development, if women are freed from all

bondages, then truly, no one can prevent nation from being into a developed country.

Discussion

Today, behind the altered image of a nation such as India, both men and women contribute significantly. Numerous instances demonstrate that women possess the capability to think, comprehend, and perform physically just like men. As many remarkable men are recognized for their roles in social transformation, similarly, the contributions of these revolutionary women are acknowledged in social progress, including figures like Savitribai Phule, Ahilayabai Holkar, Baby Kamle Bama, Urmila Pawar, Sushila Takhbore, Rajni Tilak, and Meenakshi Moon, have also made outstanding contributions. Had Savitribai Phule not advocated for education for all women, it is possible that women would still be living in ignorance today. If Ahilayabai Holkar had not fought against the practice of Sati, women might still be compelled to commit Sati alongside their husbands. If a Dalit writer like Bama and Baby Kamle had not shared her painful experiences in autobiography, many might still be unaware of the conditions of Dalit women. If a brave woman like Baby Kamle had not raised her voice for equality, Dalit women would still be forced to sit on the floor during meetings.

Conclusion

For a nation such as India to achieve peak development, it is crucial to provide women with higher education and foster their abilities in logical reasoning, scientific thought, and ethics. Additionally, women should not be confined to traditional roles like domestic responsibilities. When both genders collaborate on tasks, those endeavours are bound to succeed. Currently, this can be seen across various sectors, whether in politics, social arenas, the film industry, or businesses like shops or malls. Nowadays, societal perceptions largely rely on their fascination with women and their domestic roles. This mindset not only hampers societal growth but also serves as a significant obstacle that undermines the foundations of a developed India. Therefore, women must not be viewed merely as women, but rather acknowledged as engaged, active, and responsible individuals contributing to the nation's advancement. Such a shift in perception is essential for transforming our country's circumstances. The development of the country depends only on the change of thoughts.

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